

Impact Report 2021–2023

Open Science Office of the University of Mannheim

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Table of contents

Table of contents	1
1 Introduction	2
2 Uptake and Trends of Open Science	3
2.1 Political Context	3
2.2 Research Culture	4
3 Strategic Developments at the University of Mannheim	5
4 Impact Assessment	6
4.1 Open Science Training and Education	7
4.1.1 Key Statistics	7
4.1.2 Scope	8
4.1.3 Target Audience	9
4.1.4 Participants' Evaluation	9
4.1.5 Website and Materials	12
4.1.6 Other Points	12
4.2 Open Science Support Services	13
4.2.1 Open Science Consultation Service	13
4.2.2 Open Science Grants	17
4.3 Networking and Visibility	20
4.3.1 Networking within the University	21
4.3.2 Networking Regionally, Nationally and Internationally	21
4.3.3 Organization of Public Events	23
4.3.4 Presentations of the Open Science Office at National and International Events	23
4.4 Management Summary	25
5 Expenditure Report	26
5.1 Financial Resources	26
5.2 Personnel Resources	27
6 Future Directions	27
Data Availability Statement	29
7 Appendix	29
7.1 Open Science Timeline for the University of Mannheim	29
7.2 Course Structure of the Mannheim Master in Social Data Science	30
7.3 Questionnaire of the Participants' Evaluation from the Open Science Seminars	31

1 Introduction

Open Science as a collective term includes opening up the end stages of research (e.g. Open Access for publications, open data and research software) as well as principles of transparent and replicable research (e.g. via pre-registration, reproducible workflows). Further aspects of Open Science such as Citizen Science, Third Mission or Open Educational Resources (OER) are also increasing in importance and have an impact on society, where the research process and what is learned from research is opened up to the public. The purpose of the Open Science Office is to anchor Open Science institutionally at the University of Mannheim and have a central contact point for Open Science requests within the university. Additionally, expanding Open Science support and infrastructure for researchers institutionally, the Open Science Office aimed to increase the attractiveness of the University of Mannheim as a research location, respond to the increasing demands of third-party funders in this field and showcase our commitment to transparency and reproducibility in the research process.

On 10.09.2020 the research council unanimously recommended the establishment of an Open Science Office at the university and its funding for three years from the research fund. The rectorate then followed this recommendation on 20.09.2020 and mandated the library with the implementation of an Open Science Office. The new position of an Open Science Officer was filled by February 2021 and then again in May 2022 with a gap of 4 months in-between. The Open Science Office is operationally led by the Open Access representative and integrated within the library. Strategically the Open Science Office is advised by a newly established Open Science council since 2021. This board consists of all the members of the research council and three additional experts mostly from outside the university. The board meets at least yearly during the research council meeting and is lead by the vice-president for research.

After the initial funding of three years, it was agreed that an evaluation process will take place to decide whether the Open Science Office should be made permanent. The following report is part of this process and presents the impact of the Open Science Office since 2021. The self-evaluation is based on three core dimensions that were agreed upon by the Rectorate on 30.06.2021 following the recommendation of the Research Council:

1. Open Science Training and Education
2. Open Science Consulting and Funding
3. Networking and Visibility

Based on the reported impact on these dimensions in this impact report, the Open Science Council will make a recommendation on whether the Open Science Office should be made permanent. The final decision about the continuation of funding for the Open Science Office then needs to be made by the rectorate.

Figure 1: Organization of the Open Science Office and the parties involved at the University of Mannheim

2 Uptake and Trends of Open Science

2.1 Political Context

The topic of Open Science has been prominent on the EU’s political agenda for years. In recent years there are more and more top-down political activities around Open Science. In 2021, UNESCO published its Recommendation on Open Science¹ and Open Science became part of the latest communique of the G7 Science and Technology Ministers² in May 2023.

Consolidating such global approaches, national plans for Open Science have emerged in The Netherlands³, France⁴, Italy⁵, Ireland⁶, and Ukraine⁷ (possibly more as well) and beyond Europe. In the US, the White House — joined by 10 federal agencies, a coalition of more than 85 universities, and other organizations — declared 2023 to be a Year of Open Science⁸ to spark change and inspire Open Science engagement through events and activities. Germany have also followed suit, and in 2021 the Koalitionsvertrag⁹ also mentioned Open Science more broadly besides Open Access.

These political shifts reflect an increased weight of importance on opening up science to the public. In addition, broad and generally accessible communication of scientific research findings

¹<https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science>

²https://www8.cao.go.jp/cstp/kokusaiteki/g7_2023/230513_g7_communique.pdf

³<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433767>

⁴<https://www.ouvri.lascience.fr/second-national-plan-for-open-science-2021-2024/>

⁵<https://researchitaly.mur.gov.it/en/2022/07/15/national-plan-for-open-science-published-by-the-mur/>

⁶<https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.ff36jz222>

⁷<https://www.kmu.gov.ua/en/news/ukraina-pryiednalas-do-krajin-ies-shcho-maiut-zatverdzhnyi-plan-realizatsii-pryntsyypiv-vidkrytoi-nauky>

⁸<https://open.science.gov/>

⁹<https://open-access.network/services/news/artikel/koalitionsvertrag-2021-open-access-als-standard>

can help to raise the status and trustworthiness of science in society.

2.2 Research Culture

Some may argue that the scientific method already captures some Open Science principles. In particular, researchers expect from scientific findings – in contrast to anecdotes – that they are reproducible. However, a number of meta-analyses in medicine, psychology and other disciplines showed that this is quite often not yet the case and as a result they then coined the term replication crisis. Replication studies are now also widespread in economics and computer science. Open science practices offer solutions to the replication crisis and pave the way for the development towards transparent, open and reproducible research. Academics and academic communities in Germany are becoming increasingly active and involved in Open Science, for example, the German Psychological Society (DGPs) is committed to the ideal of transparent science¹⁰, and the Academy of Sociology calls for the provision of research data for reuse and replication to be declared the norm¹¹. In a recent study among German economists¹², there is broad agreement with the general principles of open science – but simultaneously there is a high need for support and infrastructure for Open Science activities.

Research funders have a special interest in advancing open research by providing monetary support. Therefore, they are also including Open Science in their requirements/recommendations and strategy. For example in new EU-projects (Horizon Europe) immediate Open Access for publications is required and there are also rules about research data management¹³ including the FAIRness of research data and code. The national research funding bodies DFG and BMBF are now also attaching increasing importance to factors such as open access and open data, but their strategy is more to recommend and support researchers and their managing units like libraries thereby (e.g. with money for Open Access publications). The DFG recently published a position paper “Open Science as Part of Research Culture” (2022)¹⁴ in support of Open Science. Furthermore, even regional funders like the Baden-Württemberg (BW) Stiftung ask applicants of new proposals in their elite postdoc program¹⁵ for a concept considering Open Science principles in their projects as an optional component.

Moreover, how research is assessed and evaluated during hiring or promotion processes heavily influences how researchers prioritize different research tasks which in turn has an impact on researcher engagement in Open Science. Classical methods of researcher assessment and evaluation include simple quantitative measures like the impact factor despite its misuse. Recent developments including the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA)¹⁶ and the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)¹⁷ have moved away from this

¹⁰<https://www.dgps.de/schwerpunkte/open-science/>

¹¹<https://akademie-soziologie.de/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/AS-Stellungnahme-Nachnutzung-Forschungsdaten-01-2019.pdf>

¹²<https://www.econstor.eu/handle/10419/220086>

¹³<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8089505>

¹⁴<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7194537>

¹⁵https://www.f04.uni-stuttgart.de/documents/Ausschreibung_Eliteprogramm_2022.pdf

¹⁶<https://sfdora.org/>

¹⁷<https://coara.eu/>

and have developed responsible research evaluation criteria. They call to consider all research achievements (including research data and software) and include the focus to incentivise good scientific practice (e.g. via recognition for Open Science adherence). DORA has almost 3,000 organizational signatures and CoARA has over 600 organizational signatures including the DFG and the DGP. Consequently the DGP has started to discuss requirements for future researchers including a strong focus on Open Science practices¹⁸. The DFG has already implemented small changes in the proposals and review procedures¹⁹ and has planned in the coming years to further adapt DFG’s review and evaluation procedures. To be well prepared for the coming changes that these movements produce, one needs to make PhD students and early career researchers at the University of Mannheim fit for such Open Science requirements.

3 Strategic Developments at the University of Mannheim

In recent years the University of Mannheim has included Open Science in its strategic developments in several ways which overall shows a strong commitment to Open Science at an institutional level:

- The **Open Access policy** is one of the first known strategic developments of the University of Mannheim towards Open Science. It naturally focuses on the free availability of publications, but includes research results as well: “The University of Mannheim therefore expressly advises its researchers to make their research results available to the international research community as well as to the general public through open access. Open access research results include not only original academic publications, but also research data, meta data, source materials, digital representations of pictorial and graphical materials and scholarly multimedia materials.” (Open Access Policy of the University of Mannheim²⁰, 2017)
- In July 2022, the University of Mannheim **became the first university member of the German Reproducibility Network (GRN)**, a multidisciplinary consortium advocating for more transparency in research. In the Memorandum of Understanding with the GRN adopted by the Rectorate, the University of Mannheim is committed to “the goals of transparent and inclusive research practice, open access to scientific results, and the reproducibility of research results” and assures scientists of support and further training opportunities for Open Science practices. (Press release²¹ + Rectorate meeting protocol June 2022)
- In September 2022, revised **guidelines for appointment procedures for professors (Berufungslaufplan)** of the University of Mannheim were published including the uptake on Open Science. In the text of the advertisement within appointment procedures, “it should be pointed out that the University of Mannheim attaches great importance

¹⁸<https://doi.org/10.1026/0033-3042/a000630>

¹⁹https://www.dfg.de/en/research_funding/announcements_proposals/2022/info_wissenschaft_22_61/index.html

²⁰<https://www.bib.uni-mannheim.de/en/teaching-and-research/publishing-and-open-access/open-access-policy/>

²¹<https://www.uni-mannheim.de/en/newsroom/media-relations/press-releases/2022/august/university-of-mannheim-joins-german-reproducibility-network-grn/>

to transparent and replicable research and supports these goals through open science research practices (such as pre-registration, open data, open materials, and open source).” (Guidelines for Appointment Procedures²², p. 11). Moreover, a “[p]lanned contribution to principles of transparent and trustworthy science (Open Science)” is given as an additional example of required application documents for an open position.

- The **Code of Good Research Practice** at the University of Mannheim states for research in general in §2, Paragraph 3, Point 1, Sentence 3ff that “[a]fter the publication of results, the research data, materials and information on which the results are based, the methods applied and the software used shall also be made available[...] Self-programmed software shall be made publicly available, including the source code, as far as this does not conflict with legal regulations.” Moreover, for empirical research Point 10 continues with “a) Research studies must be replicable. Accordingly, their publication must contain an as complete as possible and sufficiently detailed description of the methods of data collection, the data and software used, the statistical analysis as well as the results, which allows verification by replication. b) Research data shall be passed on after publication for reanalyses and further academic purposes, provided that no legal or contractual provisions prevent the passing on of the data. The same applies to information, applied methods and the software used.” (Code of Good Research Practice at the University of Mannheim as of 24 March 2023, own translation)
- The new **Structure and Development Plan (StEP)** of the University of Mannheim very clearly identifies the need for action to continuously promote the Open Science culture at the University of Mannheim and the role of the Open Science Office: “In the digital age, in which most scientific publications are primarily available electronically, the free accessibility, usability and further reprocessability of scientific findings and research data plays a central role. The University of Mannheim promotes the further development of the Open Science culture and has established the Open Science Office in the University Library (UB) in 2021 as a central contact and coordinating office, which is to be made permanent in 2024 upon successful evaluation.” (Structural and Development Plan (StEP) 2024-2028, p. 22, own translation)

The practical implementation of all these points are carried out by the Open Science Office.

4 Impact Assessment

The different dimensions for the evaluation of the Open Science Office were determined by its three core areas of work (i.e., Open Science Training, Support Systems and Services, and Networking and Visibility) determined by the Research Council. The evaluation criteria for these core work areas are provided underneath each section. The dimensions include both quantitative and qualitative aspects of the performance of the Open Science Office. Thus, not only the number of researchers reached and supported by the Open Science Office at the university and their subject diversity are recorded, but also the satisfaction of the researchers with the services

²²https://intranet.uni-mannheim.de/intranet/2_Formulare__Satzungen/Formulare/Berufungsleitfaden_Stand_15112022_final.pdf

of the Open Science Office. Below, data related to these evaluation dimensions are presented, demonstrating what the Open Science Office has achieved since it was founded in 2021.

4.1 Open Science Training and Education

The Open Science Training and Education evaluation dimension is defined as follows: “The Open Science Principles and Practices are made accessible to the members of the university and external researchers through concrete learning opportunities, openly available content and events within the university framework.”

This includes the following evaluation criteria:

- Number and duration of lectures, workshops and information events as well as the number of participants (see Section 4.1.1)
- Evaluation of the offers by the participants of the events (see Section 4.1.4)
- Reaching the various target groups of the university (employees, researchers, doctoral candidates and students) through training as well as the consideration of the entire spectrum of subjects in the courses (see Section 4.1.3)
- Thematic scope of the training opportunities (see Section 4.1.2)
- The provision and linking of open science content as a source of information (see Section 4.1.5)
- Number and amount of travel and conference costs covered for external open science events of scientists of the university (see Section 4.1.6)

4.1.1 Key Statistics

Between 2021 and November 2023 the Open Science Office provided 40 learning and training opportunities totalling over 70 hours. This includes 36 workshops, seminars and staff training opportunities. One summer school and 3 events also took place across 8 days. Overall over 590 participants were reached with these events (see Table 1).

Table 1: Table indicating the number of participants, duration of time spent training those participants and the number of events per type of event

	Number of Events	Duration (hours)	Participants
Invited Presentation and Workshops	6	6.50	57
Public Event	3	13.00	221
Seminar	22	21.75	211
Staff Training	4	3.75	49
Summer School	1	17.00	17
Workshop	4	10.25	37
Total	40	72.25	592

In 2022 the Open Science Office hosted an Open Science Summer School²³ in collaboration with the Graduate School of Economics and Social Sciences (GESS)²⁴ and the Research Services (Division I) where early career researchers applied to take part. Successful applicants came from a diverse range of faculties and took part in workshops designed to help them implement open science in their research.

4.1.2 Scope

The training provided spanned a broad range of topics including general Open Science (e.g. introductions, Open Science Day), reproducible and transparent research, Preregistration and Registered Reports, Open Access publishing, Open Data and Citizen Science. (See Figure 2)

Figure 2: Number of participants per training grouped by Open Science theme. Each training corresponds to a bar where the length equals the number of participants and the colour represents the year of the training.

Note that for research data management topics, the Open Science Office cooperates closely with the Research Data Center and BERD, that have a focus on data literacy training, FAIR data management, and specialized data topics (e.g. OCR, transcriptions, knowledge graphs). This collaboration allows us to focus our efforts and contributions towards training and education on further aspects like reproducibility and transparency.

²³<https://www.uni-mannheim.de/trifels-summer-school/>

²⁴<https://www.uni-mannheim.de/gess/>

4.1.3 Target Audience

The target audience can be divided into three groups:

1. The **staff training** was provided to administrative employees, librarians and colleagues from Research Services (Division I). This totals about 10% of all training opportunities provided by the Open Science Office.
2. The Open Science Day is our hallmark annual event. It is targeted towards a **mixture of audiences** including researchers, staff, students and is open for everyone. Around 170 people attended it across three years (2021²⁵, 2022²⁶, and 2023²⁷). It provides researchers opportunity to showcase Open Science practices taking place at the University of Mannheim, specifically in areas which are traditionally under-represented within Open Science including:
 - Information Systems Research (2021)
 - Romance Literary Studies (2021)
 - History (2021)
 - Ancient History (2022)
 - Computer Science (2022)
 - Economics (2023)
 - Marketing (2023)
3. The target audience for all other training opportunities (>80%) are **researchers** at all career levels. There are no detailed participants' statistics to break up researchers further into fine-grained classes, but anecdotally mostly early-career researchers have been seen in the audience.
 - Most of the training that was provided considered the entire spectrum of subjects present at the University of Mannheim since Open Science is a **cross-cutting interdisciplinary topic** that impacts research processes in most fields.
 - However, some **discipline-specific training** was also provided to address the Open Science needs of researchers in fields where standard Open Science practices prove challenging, e.g. "Transparency and Reproducibility in Qualitative Research" and "Publikationsservices und Forschungsunterstützung für das Romanische Institut".

These training opportunities are also open for students, but not many of them have yet attended. For some training opportunities they may be less likely to attend since they are not yet conducting their own research. Thus, special approaches might be needed in the future to reach them, which are outlined in Section 6.

4.1.4 Participants' Evaluation

The aforementioned Open Science Seminar Series also underwent evaluation via a short survey launched in Autumn 2023. Participants who took part in our Open Science Seminar series between Autumn 2022 and Autumn 2023 were recruited to provide their feedback. In that

²⁵<https://www.bib.uni-mannheim.de/ihre-ub/ausstellungen-und-veranstaltungen/open-science-day-2021/>

²⁶<https://www.bib.uni-mannheim.de/ihre-ub/ausstellungen-und-veranstaltungen/open-science-day-2022/>

²⁷<https://www.bib.uni-mannheim.de/ihre-ub/ausstellungen-und-veranstaltungen/open-science-day-2023/>

survey (see Section 7.3) participants were asked to indicate their career level, affiliation, discipline, which seminars they attend, and provided ratings on 5-point likert scales regarding their overall impression of the seminars (Very bad - Very Good) and their suitability given their career levels (Unsuitable - Suitable). Participants were also asked about their plans to include Open Science Practices after having attended an Open Science Seminar and to reflect on the negative and positive aspects of the series as well as what they would like to see in future seminars.

In total, just over 100 individuals who were registered to participate in those seminars between Autumn 2022 and Summer 2023 were contacted to participate via email. The number of participants who responded in that cohort totalled to 14 attendees. The low recruitment rate for that group of individuals is attributed to the following:

- The long amount of time between attending the seminar and receiving the survey.
- The email addresses that the Open Science Office has access to from the registrations are not necessarily individuals who attended seminars.
- A number of individuals attended that were not registered as they heard about our seminars through word of mouth from other colleagues.

Since, Autumn 2023 the Open Science Office began distributing the survey to attendees at the end of the seminar and will continue to do so to monitor the attendees experiences and suggestions as this is a more effective recruitment strategy.

Figure 3: Participants provided ratings on their overall impression of the Open Science Seminars (“What was your overall impression of the Open Science Seminar Series?”) and their suitability relative to their career level (“Was the level of the content suitable for your career level and background?”)

As of 20th October 2023, 20 individuals have completed the survey and in general have indicated

Figure 4: Pie chart showing the proportions of individuals indicating their use of Open Science practices after participating in the Open Science Seminar Series

the following:

- All respondents rated the Open Science Seminars as “Very good” or “good” (see Figure 3)
- Most individuals indicated that the seminars were “suitable” given their career level (see Figure 3).
- 42% of the respondents indicated that they will now use Open Science Practices in their research as a result of attending the Open Science Seminar series (see Figure 4).

Respondents also indicated the following positive aspects of the Open Science Seminar Series:

“The workshop/seminar I attended was great as we were able to directly transfer the seminar content to our own research.”
“discussing issues with open science, e.g. pre-registrations, in a safe setting”
“Very relevant topics, staff available for any questions/clarifications, meeting available also online”

Three of the respondents reported some minor negative aspects of the Open science Seminar series including the time of the seminar over running, the courses occurring during university lectures and the slides not being available (note that the slides were made available Open Science Framework²⁸ on 14.03.2023). The remaining 17 respondents did not report any negative aspects of the Open Science Office.

²⁸<https://osf.io/93zpb/files/osfstorage>

Finally, respondents suggested that they would like to see the following in our future Open Science Training and Education programs, which they were keen to do:

“Something about dealing with data/data frames/codebooks especially in interdisciplinary projects, where teams use different e.g., programmes such as R, STATA, SPSS etc. How to work together on the data well and in a for every person transparent way.”

“managing a complete open paper project, e.g. with OSF. How to pre-register, how to provide open materials, data, code, etc.”

“Maybe it would be nice to have also some more practical sessions. I really liked the session on preregistration in which we also got to apply the concepts learned to our own project. I would like to maybe have another seminar on reproducible manuscripts with some more examples on conventions and good practices to write a R script that can be easily understood also by other authors.”

These quotes reflect positively on the education and training offered thus far by the Open Science Office and indicate clear demand for continued and future training.

4.1.5 Website and Materials

There is a central website for Open Science at the University of Mannheim <https://www.uni-mannheim.de/open-science/> which is updated by the Open Science Office. Currently the website contains (i) some general information about Open Science, the Open Science Office, Events, Grants, (ii) specialized information about pre-registration, and (iii) Open Science best practices from the university.

The number of access requests were determined by the TYPO3 administrators. The total number of access requests for all Open Science Office web pages per year sum to the following:

Year	2021	2022	2023 (up to Sept. 5th)
Number of requests	65	801	702

The Open Science Office started sharing slides from the presentations on the Open Science Framework (OSF): <https://osf.io/93zpb/>. However, the statistics on this platform are limited and do not allow users to get the number of requests beyond one month prior.

4.1.6 Other Points

An initial offer was also to cover expenses for researchers when they attend external Open Science workshops or conferences. The Open Science Office posted some information on such opportunities over the mailing list, but there was only one conference fee (50 EUR) which was covered for one researcher from the university. The Open Science Office partially attributes this to the Corona crisis where opportunities to attend conferences and desire to go to them in person significantly decreased. During that time and afterwards some attempts were made to highlight this

offer but uptake did not appear to rise and therefore the Open Science Office stopped promoting that service. Another possibility for the lack of uptake is that researchers would prefer monetary support to attend longer events like summer schools (which are usually more expensive), whereas fees for attending conferences might be more readily covered by PI research funds. In the future the Open Science Office will nevertheless continue explore possibilities to support researchers attending such events, if requested, and will explore alternative avenues to advertise such as service.

4.2 Open Science Support Services

The Open Science Support Services evaluation dimension is defined as follows: “The Open Science Office supports the university’s researchers individually in integrating Open Science into their publications or third-party funding projects.” Here the key focus of evaluation is on the consultations & grants provided by the Open Science Office using the following evaluation criteria:

1. Number of individual consultations on Open Science (see Section 4.2.1.1) including target groups and range of disciplines (see Section 4.2.1.2) as well as the thematic scope (see Section 4.2.1.3).
2. Recording the satisfaction of researchers with consultations (see Section 4.2.1.4)
3. Funded projects via the Open Science Grants of the University (see Section 4.2.2.1, Section 4.2.2.2), their outcomes (see Section 4.2.2.3) and feedback to the grants (see Section 4.2.2.4).

4.2.1 Open Science Consultation Service

The Open Science Office offers individual advice and support for researchers on the following topics:

- Implementation & realization of single open science practices, e.g. preregistering research protocols and registered reports
- Open Science aspects in funding applications to the DFG, BW Stiftung or EU, especially in the planning phase
- Integration of open science practices in the research workflow to increase reproducibility and transparency, also collaboratively with various other scientists and scholars.
- Knowledge and experience of suitable research infrastructures in some Open Science practices, e.g. Open Access publishing or Open Data

Since 2022 the Open Science Office systematically counted all of those requests which are considered consultations.

4.2.1.1 Key statistics

The Open Science Office have provided around 60 consultations to researchers within the University as well as to some external stakeholders. External persons are from partner institutions e.g. from the German Reproducibility Network who are mostly interested in how Open Science is institutionalized at the University of Mannheim.

Table 3: Number of consultations per year, divided into two groups internal (i.e. from the University of Mannheim) and externals.

Internal or External	2022	2023	TOTAL
External	5	4	9
Internal	23	30	53
TOTAL	28	34	62

4.2.1.2 Target Audience

Those consultations are predominantly with researchers at the University of Mannheim but also include higher-level consultations regarding the University’s strategy towards Open Science (e.g., with the Vice President for Research, ENGAGE.EU²⁹) as well as some external stakeholders. Within the University the most requests come from social sciences followed by humanities, but other faculties have also begun to gradually approach the Open Science Office (see Table 4).

Table 4: Number of consultations per faculty.

Faculty	Number of Consultations
UMA Strategy	3
Law Studies	1
Economics	1
BWL	4
Social Sciences	24
Humanities	16
WIM	4
External	9
TOTAL	62

Table 5: Number of consultations per career level.

Career Level	Number of Consultations
Professor	17
Junior Professor	2
Post-doc	11
PhD Student	25
Other	7
TOTAL	62

²⁹<https://www.engageuniversity.eu/>

Many of our consultations are with early career researchers (including PhD students and post-doctoral researchers), however a large proportion are also made up by professors who are also increasingly interested in how they can adopt Open Science practices into their workflows (see Table 5).

4.2.1.3 Scope

While many of the consultations were about Open Access issues initially, almost two-thirds of the consultations are now also about other crucial aspects of Open Science (See Figure 5).

Figure 5: Pie chart showing the proportions of consultations which were about a particular Open Science Theme

4.2.1.4 Satisfaction (Case Studies)

In the experience of the Open Science Office the consultations always came to a positive conclusion and the Open Science Office has provided three case studies below of different consultations alongside relevant feedback where possible (see below).

Case Study 1: ENGAGE.EU

The project manager from ENGAGE.EU R&I approached the Vice President for Research and Early-Stage Researchers at the University of Mannheim who reached out to the Open Science Office to provide strategic consultation on an Open Science and Research Data action plan for the ENGAGE universities.

We provided input specifically on the timeline (which was requested by the EU) on achieving the tasks within the action plan, and gave our recommendation on what would be achievable within the remaining funding period. This timeline was essential for extending the funding period for ENGAGE.EU, which has since been granted.

Case Study 2, Junior Professor, Economic History

The Open Science Office met with a researcher and provided extensive suggestions for Open Science Practices tailored to their proposed research in an Open Science Implementation Plan for the BW Stiftung. The project was selected to be part of the “Eliteprogramm” at the University of Mannheim, so we provided extensive feedback on the Open Science Implementation plan which detailed the Open Science Practices that will be implemented at all research stages for the BW Stiftung. Following the consultations the Junior Professor at hand said:

“Many thanks for these really useful edits and comments! I’ve incorporated the changes you suggest and the proposal is now a lot stronger.”

The proposal is currently under review at the BW Stiftung.

Case Study 3, PhD student, Social Sciences

A PhD student approached us on the recommendation of a colleague with the following questions: “One of my articles was published in an APA journal. Prior to publication, I published a preprint in PsyArXiv with the consent of the journal. May I attach this preprint to my dissertation and make it available in print and in electronic form (e.g. MADOC^a)? We could find together a good way to include a version of all three articles forming the publications-based dissertation and make it available under Open Access. Thereby, we also discussed how exactly in this case the publishing duty of the dissertation can be fulfilled without violating any copyright claims. For more practical questions about the few printed copies to hand in, we could refer to a colleague in the library responsible for that.

The PhD student was thankful and wrote:

“I am very happy with the extremely helpful service of the Open Science Office. They responded very quick and answered all my questions related to copyright issues in detail.”

^a<https://madoc.bib.uni-mannheim.de/>

These case studies demonstrate the depth of the consultations offered by the Open Science Office, how they implement Open Science into each stage of the research workflow, and finally

the positive impressions which researchers at the University of Mannheim have of the Open Science Consultation service.

4.2.2 Open Science Grants

Beyond Open Science consultations, at the University of Mannheim researchers are eligible to apply for the Open Science Grants (max. 5.000 EUR per project) which take place annually. Beyond describing their research, the Open Science Grants also require applicants to explain how they will implement Open Science practices and present their overall vision for Open Science in their project. In doing so, these grants ensure that other Open Science aspects of the research process (e.g., pre-registration, sharing data and code openly) are rewarded and encouraged, which would otherwise go unrecognized.

4.2.2.1 Key Statistics

There were 36 applications for the calls for these Open Science grants in 2021 and 2022. Out of these, applications 12 projects were awarded an Open Science Grant (acceptance rate: 33%).

Table 6: The number of projects and amount of funding applied for and awarded in the 2021 and 2022 Open Science grant rounds.

Year	Total Applications	Funded Projects	Funding Applied	Funding Awarded
2021	20	8	84,621.70 EUR	28,737.00 EUR
2022	16	4	73,242.88 EUR	18,440.00 EUR
All	36	12	157,864.58 EUR	47,177.00 EUR

Overall researchers applied for 157,864.58 EUR in research funding for their Open Science projects and 47,177.00 EUR was awarded in research funding (see Table 6 for further details).

4.2.2.2 Target audience

Most applications came from early career researchers such as PhD students who typically do not have the opportunity to apply for research funding (see Figure 6a). Post-doctoral researchers were more likely to be funded, followed by PhD students.

Successful applications came from a diverse set of faculties. Psychology received the most number of successful applications, but 60% of successful applications came from other faculties (e.g., Political Sciences, Linguistics, see Figure 6b).

4.2.2.3 Outcomes

Out of the first round of the Open Science Grants in 2021, six projects have now been completed, one is still ongoing and one was discontinued. Several publications have been written out of these projects which are either published or currently under review (and more are likely to follow):

Figure 6: Open Science Grant applications and funded projects. (a) Number of successful and unsuccessful Open Science Grant applications by career level. (b) Number of funded applications per faculty at the University of Mannheim.

- Ingendahl, M., Maschmann, I. T., Embs, N., Maulbetsch, A., Vogel, T., & Wänke, M. (2023). Articulation dynamics and evaluative conditioning: investigating the boundary conditions, mental representation, and origin of the in-out effect. *Cognition and Emotion*, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02699931.2023.2228538>
- Nadarevic, L., & Kias, A. (2021, October 6). Color-validity associations put to the test: Examining the robustness of red-false and green-true associations in the Implicit Association Test. Preprint <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/qa6e9>
- Chan, C. & Freudenthaler, R. (under review). A benchmark dataset for detecting frames in multi-topical news content.
 - This work was presented at the Annual ICA Conference 2023 and won there the top paper award from the the Computational Methods division of the International Communication Association³⁰.

Besides these classical form of research outcomes through publications, many other research outcomes were produced and shared by these Open Science Projects (including a Bachelor Thesis and PhD thesis as well as Open Data and Code, Pre-registrations, and Registered Reports; see Table 7).

³⁰https://sciences.social/@ica_cm/110441322419208171

Table 7: The number of Open Science Deliverables produced by Open Science Grant awardees from 2021

Open Science Deliverable	No. of Deliverables
Open Data	9
Open Code	4
Open Materials	8
Preregistration	10
Registered Report	0
Publications	3
Conference Presentations	11
Conference Posters	2

Beyond that, one successful grant application yielded a large number of new Open Educational resources³¹ as part of a tandem seminar funded by the Open Science Grant at the University of Mannheim³². Moreover the Mannheim Open Science Meetup, a multidisciplinary grass roots initiative for individuals in Mannheim and the local area that supports Open Science, which is funded and supported by an Open Science Grant, has organized over 50 meetings presenting and discussing Open Science topics.

4.2.2.4 Feedback

The Open Science Grants were presented at a European conference, the Open Science FAIR (2023)³³. This presentation was one of 24 presentations selected out of 63 to be delivered at this conference. The following positive feedback was given by the two reviewers of the presentation proposal:

“It is extremely valuable that the institution specifically supports and encourages research evaluation processes related to open science. All participants should see this example.” - Reviewer 1

“This proposal presents institutional grants to reward open aspects of the scholarly process, that are usually not recognised, with a view to incentivise research practices that advance OS (e.g., openly sharing data and/or code, registrations) in the university. Those grants connect open science in general with the reform of research assessment. It is a good idea to incentivise open research practices with those individual grants. In turn, the grants can be recognised as part of the CV. In addition, this proposal addresses EDI issues and considers the specific challenges and needs of early-career researchers.” - Reviewer 2.

³¹https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:Hochschulprogramm/Mannheim_FSS_2022

³²<https://www.phil.uni-mannheim.de/germanistische-linguistik/forschung/tandem-seminar-im-open-science-format/>

³³<https://www.opensciencefair.eu>

Relatedly the 2021 awardees also provided some positive feedback about the Open Science Grants themselves which consolidated the opinion of the two aforementioned reviewers:

“This paper would not have existed without this programme. This is a unique opportunity, especially for doctoral students, to carry out clean and replicable research without being financially dependent on their supervisors.” - **Open Science Grant 2021 awardee**

Indeed, when asked about their experience of having been awarded the Open Science Grants in 2021, awardees also said the following:

“I think the Open Science Grant was an incredible opportunity for me as a junior researcher to plan, develop, and conduct research independently - while simultaneously adhering to the highest scientific standards. When you do research as a PhD student in experimental psychology your chances to succeed in academia very much depend on how much money your department head is willing or able to spend. I think that this format of an Open Science Grant is an excellent way to help junior researchers gain some independence, and by the same token, to get open science practices in the daily routine of the next generation of researchers. In academic currency, the grant has most likely brought me one first-authored multi-study paper in a very good journal.” - **Open Science Grant 2021 awardee 1**

“We had the opportunity to pre-register a study without having to worry about how to recruit and pay the large number of participants needed to conduct the study. Without this grant, we would not have been able to realize the pre-registered experiment.” - **Open Science Grant 2021 awardee 2**

“It would just be great if the possibility to apply for Open Science Grants of the University of Mannheim remains.” - **Open Science Grant 2021 awardee 3**

The grants awarded in 2022 are currently underway and are expected to be completed by the end of 2023 and will address the following Open Science themes: Preregistration, open data, open code, open access, citizen science, and science communication.

4.3 Networking and Visibility

The Open Science Networking and Visibility evaluation dimension is defined as follows: “The Open Science Office strives to network with similar actors at the university, regional, national and international level in order to support the visibility of the university and to use synergy effects.”

The following evaluation criteria related to this include the following:

- Status of networking within the university e.g. with the Research Services from Division I, FDZ, MZES, MCDS (see Section 4.3.1), regionally (e.g. with the cross-institutional

Mannheim Open Science Meetup), nationally or internationally (e.g. via ENGAGE.EU) (see Section 4.3.2)

- Organization of public events e.g. Mannheim Open Science Day, co-organization of the Trifels Summer School on Open Science (see Section 4.3.3)
- Presentation of the Open Science Office at national and international events on Open Science in order to increase the visibility and networking of the university (see Section 4.3.4)

4.3.1 Networking within the University

- The Open Science Office was present at the following **university-wide networking events** (sometimes in tandem with the library):
 - 27.10.2021: Welcome Event for PhD students (online)
 - 01.06.2022: Professorium (barbecue, information stand)
 - 09.05.2023: Klausurtagung - Roadshow Lehre
 - 24.05.2023: Professorium (barbecue, information stand)
 - 13.10.2023: Nachwuchsfrühstück
 - several talks within welcome rounds for new professors organized by Research Services from Division I (previously named “Toolboxgespräche”)
- The **research data center (FDZ)** and Open Science Office are both integrated in the library and have manifold connections and exchanges. They are now jointly presenting their courses under the label Research Skills³⁴ and promoting them together.
- Training for staff members in **Research Services (Division I)** has been provided and knowledge exchange has taken place to facilitate the interaction between the departments to assist researchers (e.g., assisting Division I with Open Science aspects of researchers funding applications; see also case studies). Division I have now also been provided with a pamphlet which they can provide researchers who are interested in our services and who wish to reach out to us.
- The Open Science Office is currently engaged with the **Council of Doctoral Candidates** at the University of Mannheim to establish an Open Science Program tailored to the diverse needs of PhD students from various faculties.

4.3.2 Networking Regionally, Nationally and Internationally

- The Open Science Office supports, on a regional level, the **Mannheim Open Science Meetup** (an interdisciplinary grassroots initiative for Open Science). The Open Science Office provides both organizational support as well as financial help (e.g. travel cost for external speakers) through their Open Science Grant for their monthly meetups.
- The University of Mannheim has become the first university to become a member of the **German Reproducibility Network (GRN)**, a German interdisciplinary consortium of research initiatives and institutes working towards Open and Reproducible research. This

³⁴<https://www.bib.uni-mannheim.de/en/teaching-and-research/research-skills/>

partnership was covered by the local news, Mannheimer Morgen³⁵. The GRN is part of a larger network of international Reproducibility networks including the United Kingdom Reproducibility Network and Australian Reproducibility Network. Since the university joined the GRN the following has been achieved:

- The current Open Science Officer has been appointed as an Academic Coordinator for Research Improvement, and represents the university at member meetings and elections.
- The Open Science Officer has also recently been elected to the steering committee of the GRN where he is responsible for Community Development, recruiting likeminded universities and research institutions that are prospective members of the GRN. This is achieved by using his experience of running an Open Science Office at a university and applying for institutional membership on behalf of the University of Mannheim.
- The Open Science Office has also collaborated with the GRN members and other like-minded researchers on a publication about strategies for making reproducible research and open science training the norm at research institutions with useful tips for the practical implementation: Kohrs, F. E., Auer, S., Bannach-Brown, A., Fiedler, S., Haven, T. L., Heise, V., ... Zumstein, P., Weissgerber, T. L. (2023). Eleven Strategies for Making Reproducible Research and Open Science Training the Norm at Research Institutions. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/kcvra>
- Moreover, the Open Science Office is actively involved in the **European University ENGAGE.EU project**, which consists of 9 partner universities including the University of Mannheim. The Open Science Seminars are open also for all partner universities from the consortia (and beyond) and are announced over the ENGAGE community platform³⁶ as well. The Open Science Office has also hosted a colleague for job shadowing from our partner Université Toulouse Capitole (UT1) alongside the Research Data Center. The Open Science Office was involved in the following ENGAGE.EU tasks and work packages:
 - WP 4 Engaging Society (during the proposal period + kick-off)
 - Task 3.2 (part of the working group)
 - Task 3.5 (feedback for the Open Science matrix)
 - Task 3.1 (bibliometric analysis and feedback)
 - R+I WP 5 Data Management and Open Science (during the proposal period, part of the working group)
 - R+I Task 2.4 (help with first deliverable)
- The Open Science Office was chosen to be part of the **Second Open Science Retreat** (Sustainable and reliable Open Science Infrastructures and Tools) organized by the ZBW – Leibniz Information Centre for Economics in February 2022.
- The head librarian was invited for an **interview about the competencies for Open**

³⁵https://www.mannheimer-morgen.de/orte/mannheim_artikel,-mannheim-foerderung-von-transparenz-_arid,1986733.html

³⁶<https://www.research-community-engage.eu/events>

Science Services in libraries, which is part of a study commissioned by LIBER (the Association of European Research Libraries) and by ADBU the Association of directors of university libraries in France. During the conversation, it was mentioned that Mannheim is the only German university library that has been approached for this topic so far.

- The Open Science Office was invited as **reviewers for the Open Science Conference 2023**.
- The Open Science Office was **invited** by the SLUB Dresden to their opening of an Open Science Labs as well as to the launch of Berlin Universities Publishing (BerlinUP), the new publishing house for the Freie Universität Berlin, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Technische Universität Berlin and Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin. Finally, in recent months the Open Science Office has been **in contact with several institutions** providing advice on setting up comparable Open Science Offices within Germany stapling the University of Mannheim as a key point of contact for adopting Open Science at an institutional level.

4.3.3 Organization of Public Events

Over the past three years the Open Science Office has held its landmark public event, the Open Science Day, in 2021, 2022, and 2023. Year on year the number of participants in these events has continued to grow since the Open Science Office was founded. The organization of this event involves the search and invitation of keynote speakers and other speakers, reserving the room, organizing the catering, creating a website, distributing the invitations over a variety of communication channels, financial compensation of external speakers, as well as the moderation and technical handling on the event day.

The Open Science Office collaborated with GESS to organize the Trifels Summer School on Open Science (2022)³⁷. The Open Science Office was responsible for and assisted with:

- Organising and preparing the Open Science Program by recruiting speakers
- Reviewing applications to participate in the summer school
- Delivering workshops to the summer schools participants
- The yearly panel discussion “Trifelser Gespräch” during the Trifels Summer School was organized in 2022 by the University of Mannheim. This panel discussion, by design, sought for exchange with the local public. The topic “Mit Open Science globalen Krisen begegnen – Offenheit und Transparenz in der Wissenschaft” was chosen for this year’s panel discussion.

4.3.4 Presentations of the Open Science Office at National and International Events

The Open Science Office continues to increase the visibility of the University of Mannheim as an Open Science stakeholder having presented its approaches and achievements at conferences across Germany and beyond:

- Maschmann, I. T., Zumstein, P, & Erdfelder, E. (2021). The Open Science Office of the University of Mannheim: Supporting Researchers Beyond Open Access and Research Data

³⁷<https://www.uni-mannheim.de/trifels-summer-school/>

Management. OAI - The Geneva Workshop on Innovations in Scholarly Communication (OAI12) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5479586>

- Maschmann, I. T., & Zumstein, P. (2022). Open Science Services an Hochschulen und Forschungsinstitutionen verankern. Bibliothekskongress. Leipzig. urn:nbn:de:0290-opus4-180165³⁸
- Morgan, D. P. & Zumstein, P. (2022). The past, the present and the future of the University of Mannheim's Open Science Office. Open Science Festival 2022. Leibniz University, Hannover, Germany. urn:nbn:de:bsz:180-madoc-634312³⁹
- Zumstein, P., & Morgan, D. P. (2022). Das Open Science Office der Universität Mannheim: Ein ganzheitliches, interdisziplinäres Angebot von Open Science Services. Open Access Tage 2022 (OAT22), Bern. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6961731>
- Morgan, D. P. & Zumstein, P. (2023). Integrating a mandatory and hands-on course on open science and reproducible research into the curriculum for the Mannheim Master in Social Data Science. Reproducible research: Education and Teaching formats, reports from the reproducibility networks. Berlin Institute of Health @ Charité, Berlin, Germany. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7974050>
- Morgan, D. P. & Zumstein, P. (2023). University-led funding to foster transparent and reproducible research practices across disciplines. Open Science FAIR 2023. Madrid, Spain. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8402797>
- Schader, A., Zumstein, P., & Morgan, D. P. (2023). The German Reproducibility Network (GRN). What is it and why is it worth joining? International Data Week 2023: A Festival of Data. Salzburg, Austria. <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rdas-21st-plenary-poster-exhibition>

In addition, Open Science Office contributed to three publications:

- Morgan, D.P. (2022). The Goldilocks zone of sample size: Getting it just right. Psychonomic Society, Featured Content, Scientific Practice, Statistics and Methodology. <https://featuredcontent.psychonomic.org/the-goldilocks-zone-of-sample-size-getting-it-just-right/>
- Zumstein, P. (2022). Blitzschnelles Publizieren mit Academia Letters, aber sag', wie verhält es sich mit der Qualitätssicherung? Ein informationswissenschaftlicher Kommentar. LIBREAS. Library Ideas, 41. <https://libreas.eu/ausgabe41/zumstein/>
- Kohrs, F. E., Auer, S., Bannach-Brown, A., Fiedler, S., Haven, T. L., Heise, V., ... Zumstein, P., Weissgerber, T. L. (2023, May 28). Eleven Strategies for Making Reproducible Research and Open Science Training the Norm at Research Institutions. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/kcvra>

³⁸<https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:0290-opus4-180165>

³⁹<https://madoc.bib.uni-mannheim.de/63431/>

4.4 Management Summary

The Open Science Office **has provided over 70 hours of training and educational opportunities to almost 600 individuals** since 2021, which have been received positively with many researchers requesting further training on new topics on upcoming challenges with regards to Open Science. Crucially, the Open Science Training and Education program provided by the Open Science Office has not only drawn in those currently engaging but also researchers who have not done Open Science before and who now as a result of the seminars can take up Open Science practices in their research.

Beyond training and education, the Open Science Office has provided over **60 Open Science consultations** since 2022, supporting researchers at the university from diverse subjects and all target groups with integrating Open Science into their research. The consulted researchers (including professors and the rectorate) have given very positive feedback to the Open Science Office. The consultations emerged mainly in the context of third-party funded projects, daily research work, and also the advancement of early-career researchers.

So far there were two rounds of university-wide Open Science Grants, where the Open Science Office organizes the calls for proposals, the review process and the distribution of funds and accompanies the projects throughout their entire duration. Thereby **12 projects were awarded** (out of 36 applications) with a maximum of 5.000 EUR. Six projects are now finished and they, together with the ongoing and funded Mannheim Open Science Meetup, **have provided over 100 deliverables related to Open Science Practices**, which include publications, conference contributions, pre-registrations, open data, and open code. This approach which both encouraged and rewarded researchers for engaging in Open Science Practices and provided them with funding and publication experience for their CVs has proved successful and has been well received both internally by awardees and externally when presenting the grants at an international conference.

The Open Science Office has networked with like-minded actors at the university, regional, national, and international level in order to support the visibility of the university and to use synergy effects. It represents the University of Mannheim in the German Reproducibility Network and is active in the Mannheim Open Science Meetup and ENGAGE.EU. **The university's approach to Open Science has been presented at 6 conferences** and 3 publications have been written. Furthermore, several public events like the Open Science Day and a public podium discussion have been organized.

Overall, the Open Science Office achieved **impact in all evaluation dimensions**. It implemented and advanced the strategic goals of the University of Mannheim regarding Open Science.

5 Expenditure Report

5.1 Financial Resources

	2021	2022	2023	TOTAL
Personnel expenditure	14.720,05 €	26.207,26 €	26.268,62 €	67.195,93 €
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2021: 6 months 25% + 5 months 50% • 2022: 8 months 50% • 2023: 8 months 50% (so far) 				
Own travel expenses + participation fees	100,00 €	97,00 €	981,73 €	1.178,73 €
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 x Open Science Conference 2021 (online) • Open Science Festival 2022 (Hannover) • Open Science Festival NL 2022 (Amsterdam) • 3 x Open Science Conference 2022 (online) • GRN Symposium (Berlin) • Open Science FAIR 2023 (Madrid) 				
Open Science Grants	26.537,00 €		18.440,00 €	44.977,00 €
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8 awarded projects 2021 • 4 awarded projects 2022/2023 				
Printing cost		15,21 €		15,21 €
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poster for Open Science Festival 2022 				
External workshop leaders and speakers		1.234,13 €	67,30 €	1.301,43 €
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ReproHack 2022 • Open Science Day 2022 				
Catering cost		910,16 €		910,16 €
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Science Day 2022 				
Expenditures of the Open Science Meetup (total of 2.000 EUR are approved as a grant, centrally managed)			61,65 €	61,65 €

5.2 Personnel Resources

The Open Science Office was initially planned with a 0,5 FTE TV-L E13 position (Open Science Officer) and it was decided to cover these costs from the research fund for 3 years. In addition the university library agreed to provide personnel resources from its own staff. Overall the planned personnel resources were:

- 0,5 E13 Open Science Officer
- 0,3 A14/E13 Open Access representative, subject librarian for social science (library resources)
- 0,2 E9 several people from publishing services, finance department, digital library services, media design (library resources)

While the estimated personal resources from the library for supporting activities were sufficient, the need for core tasks (especially for the Open Access representative) was significantly underestimated - the actual human input in this area was approximately twice as high. As this was not sustainable in the longer term, the rectorate approved a full E13 position for the Open Science Office in February 2023, initially with a term from 01 July to 31 December 2025. The library will additionally continue to put approximately 0.5 FTE from its own staff distributed over several persons to the Open Science Office.

6 Future Directions

The **current service portfolio** is well received (cf. Section 4) and should therefore be continued and further developed. The core of the service portfolio will continue to be training and further education opportunities as well as individual consultations and support services for researchers. The Open Science Grants have proven their worth as an instrument for funding specific research projects related to Open Science and therefore should continue. A focus will be on supporting young researchers in empirically oriented subject areas, while at the same time taking into account the other subject-specific needs and requirements of all researchers.

It is expected that the number of consultation request will increase in the future as the information of such a service usually spreads only very slowly to the university members overall and the requirements or expectations towards a more open, transparent, reproducible and inclusive research are increasing. Some questions in the consultations are posed repeatedly, also the individual situation is almost always different. It then should still be possible to collect some general advice and write this up as **guidelines** shared online. Moreover, the content of the Open Science website can also be extended and covering more topics.

In the future the Open Science Office also plans to consider further **subject-specific needs** following also the suggestions from the meeting of the Open Science Council in November 2022. There were already some discipline-specific trainings that should be expanded with respect to the subjects. The Open Science Office sees a more intensive communication with the departments and networking with key persons crucial for understanding the subject-specific approaches to Open Science and the needs to support them. Similar demands are also becoming apparent in

the area of research data management. Therefore, the Open Science Office already maintains a close exchange with the Research Data Centre at the library and will be involved in further networking activities.

Furthermore, the Open Science topics should also be anchored in teaching, especially at Master's level. For students at **Bachelor's level**, it is first important to gain a general understanding of Open Science without already going deeper into subject-specific features. At this level, Open Science can be considered as a partial aspect of **Data Literacy**. A cross-disciplinary data literacy offer is planned by teaching and learning center (ZLL) and the library; the Open Science Office will provide input here at appropriate points.

At the **Master's level**, an in-depth, research-oriented engagement with open science methods can make sense, especially in data-oriented degree programmes such as the **Mannheim Master for Social Data Science (MMSDS)**, which will start in 2024. In this interdisciplinary degree programme, which is jointly organized by the social sciences and business informatics and mathematics, empirical methods relevant to the social sciences are to be studied in depth. For this degree programme, the Open Science Office has already developed a rough concept for a dedicated course on "Open Science & Reproducible Research", which it plans to run annually from 2024 (cf. the presentation at a knowledge exchange symposium⁴⁰). The course will be compulsory for the MMSDS programme and therein part of the "Foundation to Data Science" (see Figure 7 in the appendix).

In **graduate training**, elements of the Master's course could be combined with research data management topics and offered through the Graduate School (GESS). However, the resources for the development of a corresponding concept and the continuous implementation of corresponding courses are beyond what the Open Science Office can do with the current personnel resources at the moment.

Finally, the activities for **networking** in national and international context are important to continue. Besides synergy effects they help to increase the **visibility** of the University of Mannheim and its strategic positioning. Other activities for increasing visibility are conceivable such as sharing a report like this.

⁴⁰<https://zenodo.org/record/7974050>

Data Availability Statement

The raw data of this report can be accessed via the two attached Excel files which came as part of the package for this Open Science Impact Report:

1. OSO_ImpactData.xlsx
 - Sheet **Consultations**: Anonymized data about all consultations since 2022 as presented in Section 4.2.1.
 - Sheet **Training**: Data about all training and education opportunities as presented in Section 4.1.
 - Sheet **Grants**: Partially anonymized data about the Open Science Grants as presented in Section 4.2.2.
 - Sheet **Grant Deliverables**: Detailed list of the deliverables from the finished grants as presented in Section 4.2.2.3.
2. 20-10-2023_OSSeminar_Feedback.xlsx
 - Data from the online participants' evaluation survey (see Section 7.3 for the questionnaire, data as of 20.10.2023) as presented in Section 4.1.4.

7 Appendix

7.1 Open Science Timeline for the University of Mannheim

date	description
10.09.2020	Establishment of an Open Science Office (recommendation research council)
30.09.2020	Establishment of an Open Science Office (decision rectorate)
01.02.2021	Ira Maschmann starts as the new Open Science Officer
30.06.2021	Agreement on the evaluation dimensions (decision rectorate)
June 2021	Formation of the Open Science council with three additional experts is completed
01.01.2022	Open Science Officer position is vacant
01.05.2022	David Philip Morgan starts as the new Open Science Officer
June 2022	The University of Mannheim joined the German Reproducibility Network (GRN)
Sept. 2022	Open Science is anchored in the guidelines for appointments of professors
24.11.2022	Interim report is discussed (Open Science council)
Feb. 2023	Increase the position to 100% E13 until 2025 (decision rectorate)
July 2023	Structure and development plan of the university (StEP 2024-2028) confirms clearly the need for action to continuously promote the Open Science culture at the University of Mannheim and the role of the Open Science Office
16.11.2023	Evaluation meeting of the Open Science Office with the council
2024	Continuation of the Open Science Office will be decided

7.2 Course Structure of the Mannheim Master in Social Data Science

Figure 7: Mannheim Masters in Social Data Science, Course Structure. Open Science and Reproducibility is a Foundation of Data Science

Open Science Seminar Series Feedback Form

Open Science Office

We have distributed this form to you as you may have participated in one of our Open Science Seminars provided by the Open Science Office at the University of Mannheim. We are very interested in getting your feedback about the seminar series and would like to learn what you would like to see next.

We thank you in advance for your participation in this survey and for your helpful feedback.

If you have any questions about this feedback survey please feel free to contact me using the details provided below.

Rationale for this feedback survey:

This feedback will form part of the basis for determining the *evaluation* of the Open Science Office and the services it provides (e.g., teaching, funding and Open Science consulting) beyond 2024. We will use the feedback you provide in the impact report which we are currently writing for the Open Science Office. This impact report will be handed to the research council of the University of Mannheim to review the performance of the Open Science Office.

David Philip Morgan (Open Science Officer and Research Data Management Consultant @ UB Mannheim)

Email: david.morgan(at)uni-mannheim.de

There are 11 questions in this survey.

Open Science Seminar Series, Feedback Survey

Data Protection Notice and Consent (Please read the following)

Before you answer the Open Science Office's online survey and provide feedback on the Open Science Seminar Series, we would like to inform you about our privacy policy. Only after giving your consent, will you be directed to the online survey. Your participation is voluntary. You will not suffer any disadvantages if you do not wish to participate.

The following data collected and used in this survey that may be considered personal under GDPR are

the following:

- Career Level
- Faculty

To preserve the anonymity of this personal data you will not be known by name and will instead be assigned an anonymized participation number. In addition neither your email address or name used to contact you will be associated with your anonymized participation number.

The relevant legal basis for the data processing is consent, Art. 6 1 (a) GDPR.

The aggregated data collected in this survey will may be made publicly available alongside the the impact report which will present that data. The data may also be used in further presentations, posters or publications from the Open Science Office.

Data collection in this survey is done under a secure connection via HTTPS certificate meaning that all data transmission to our database located on the servers at the University of Mannheim, UB Mannheim is encrypted.

You can exercise your right of revocation of your data at any time without giving reasons and revoke the declaration of consent given with effect for the future. The lawfulness of the processing based on your consent remains unaffected until receipt of your revocation. Please note that due to the anonymous collection, data records cannot be assigned to a person. The correction or deletion of your data entered in the survey in the event of a revocation of consent is therefore not possible without further ado.

If you wish to do so, you may leave the survey at anytime by closing the tab in your browser or the browser itself. If you do not consent to the processing of your data, you did not understand the information provided or do not agree for the data collected in this survey to be used by the Open Science Office in the manor stated above please close the browser or tab in which the survey is open.

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

Please select the following if you wish to participate:

I have read and understood the information on processing and my rights in full and have no objections.

I hereby declare my consent to the processing of my personal data collected

by the Open Science
Office within the
framework of this
online survey under
the conditions stated
above and in the
University of Mannheim's
data protection
declaration.

Open Science Seminar Feedback

What is your career level? *

Choose one of the following answers

If you choose 'Other:' please also specify your choice in the accompanying text field.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- PhD Student
- Post-doctoral Researcher
- Junior Professor
- Professor
- Research Support (Librarian, Administration, IT)

Other

Which discipline do you belong to? *

Please write your answer here:

Are you affiliated with the University of Mannheim? *

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Do not wish to state

Of the Open Science Seminars which you attended, what were the Open Science Theme(s)? *

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Reproducibility and Transparency (inc. preregistrations and registered reports)
- Open Data/Research Data Management
- Open Access
- Third Mission or Citizen Science
- Other:

Please answer the following: *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Very bad	Bad	Neutral	Good	Very Good
What was your overall impression of the Open Science Seminar Series?	<input type="radio"/>				

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Somewhat Unsuitable	somewhat unsuitable	Neutral	Somewhat suitable	Suitable
Was the level of the content suitable for your career level and background?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Are you planning to include Open Science Practices in your next research project and/or publication?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes, I was already using Open Science practices prior to attending.
- Yes, I have decided to use Open Science practices after attending.
- Not sure
- No

What are the negative aspects about the Open Science Seminar Series?

Please write your answer here:

Any feedback from you is very much appreciated and will help us in our evaluation process as well as future plans

What are the positive aspects of the Open Science Seminar Series?

Please write your answer here:

Any feedback from you is very much appreciated and will help us in our evaluation process as well as future plans

Which topics would you like the Open Science Office Seminar Series to cover next?

Please write your answer here:

Any feedback from you is very much appreciated and will help us in our evaluation process as well as future plans

Thank you for participating in this survey. If you require any further help with Open Science, please feel free to contact me by email @ [david.morgan\(at\)uni-mannheim.de](mailto:david.morgan@uni-mannheim.de).

You may now close the tab or browser.

10-31-2023 – 14:58

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.